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FEATURES OF THE MANIFESTATION OF ARISTOTLE'S DOCTRINE OF MOTION IN THE ONTOLOGY OF FAKHR AL-DIN AL-RAZI

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Abstract: This article analyzes Aristotle's philosophical views on motion and their interpretation in Fahriddin ar-Razi's ontology. Aristotle interpreted motion as “the process of transition from possibility to reality”, considering it an integral characteristic of material existence. Fahriddin ar-Razi deeply studied these views and harmonized them with Islamic doctrinal foundations. He incorporated Aristotle's teachings on causality, time, and types of motion into his philosophy and reinterpreted them with the teachings of the Holy Quran. The study reveals the similarities and differences between the views of Aristotle and Ar-Razi, their significance in the development of Islamic philosophy.

Keywords: Aristotle, Fahriddin ar-Razi, ontology, the doctrine of motion, possibility and reality, causality, time, Islamic philosophy, kalam.

In ancient Greek philosophy, Aristotle interpreted motion as “the process of transition from possibility to reality”, explaining it as an integral characteristic of material existence. The great thinker of the medieval Muslim world, Fahriddin ar-Razi, deeply studied these views and harmonized them with the dogmatic foundations of Islam. Although Aristotle's ideas about causality and motion are significantly reflected in his ontology, he enriched them with new content by adapting them to Islamic teachings. Therefore, the study of the peculiarities of the manifestation of Aristotle's views in the doctrine of movement of al-Razi is one of the important scientific issues.

Agreeing with Aristotle's definitions of motion, Razi argues that existence, that is, everything that exists, cannot be only possible (potential) in all respects, exists either in the form of existents or in the form of complete reality (actuality), that is, in the form of turning one's existing possibility into reality (according to Razi, this is only Allah) or in the form of possibility on the one hand, and reality on the other. Thus, according to Razi, the reality of action is either the emergence or acceptance, or the gradual, evolutionary, or instantaneous transition from possibility to reality.

According to Aristotle, the truth of motion manifests itself only in the orientation towards something else. According to Razi's definition of the concept of motion, based on Aristotle's views, it has two characteristics:

1) For an action to be directed, there must be something aimed at in the direction it is directed.

2) Since movement continues, there must certainly be a possibility for it, and since this possibility has not yet become reality, the movement continues.

Thus, the definition of action depends on what is preserved in possibility, and the purpose of action is to turn this possibility into reality. However, in perfection that has become complete reality, neither of these two characteristics is found, and it has no need for action.

Knowing this, if we say that an object is located in one place, then it is possible for that object to be in another place, to occupy another space. In this case, there are two possibilities for the action to take place:

1) The first is to occupy another space right there, and the second is to move towards that space, that is, not to fully occupy the space, but to begin action for this purpose.

2) Secondly, in possibility, that is, in the direction of space, the transformation of possibility into reality is carried out not through occupying space, but through the transformation of the possibility of directing towards it into reality. Consequently, action itself is the first achieved perfection in terms of the transformation of possibility into reality.

Razi considers action based on four categories. They are quantity, quality, space, and position. () In the form of quantity, movement manifests itself in two ways. These are: The first is contraction or expansion, and the second is growth.

During these processes, Razi, who drew attention to the fact that when movement occurs, a state of decrease or expansion occurs in the body without separating or adding anything, gives an example of a water-filled bag to explain this movement. The more water you put in the waterskin, the wider it becomes. Or if we freeze the water inside the waterskin, the waterskin will narrow. In both cases, no other substance was added to the mesh from the outside, for example, the leather used in its manufacture, nor was it removed from its composition. However, the main issue here is the return of water to its natural state with the removal of water from the mesh. Other bodies, for example, ceramic vessels, can only be filled with a certain amount of water or other substance. If the pressure exceeds the limit, the clay vessel will break, just as the mesh will break, and the expansion of each body will occur only to a certain extent, parallel to the process of the body returning to its natural state.

Another way of action, related to quantity, is growth and destruction. In this case, the body enters into contact with another body, and certain parts of that

body transition to this body or acquire similarity to its nature, resulting in this type of motion related to quantity.

Some philosophers before Razi rejected qualitative changes in the body and put forward the idea that this movement is a change in the essence of the body and that it is impossible to change the essence. Razi rejects this idea, defending the view that if the change in a body occurs gradually, this change is possible and we call it motion.

The manifestation of motion in space and position occurs due to changes in the parts that make up the body relative to other bodies. Just as with the Celestial sphere, which does not occupy any specific space, or with bodies other than the celestial sphere occupied by space, if they are set in motion, this phenomenon is not actually spatial, but rather occurs due to a change in the ratio of matter (huwiyya) to another external body, whether within or outside the body. Therefore, this type of motion in the body occurs relatively positively.

Razi opposes the view that the universe moves in space because the bodies existing in the universe and their parts move in space, stating that "this view is incorrect because the reality of the whole differs from the reality of the part, and the order existing for the part is not required to apply to the whole." For example, even if sand particles in the desert change their positions and one occupy the space of another, the desert as a whole remains motionless in space.

From Razi's thoughts, it can be concluded that if a body is not moving, then it either appears continuously in a certain space or does not move despite the possibility of movement in its nature. This idea is the exact form of the first law developed by Isaac Newton, the founder of modern physics, and Fahriddin al-Razi reached this idea almost five centuries before him, but did not form these ideas as a separate concept. This issue also indicates how deep knowledge lies at the heart of the insufficiently studied views of representatives of Islamic philosophy, such as Razi.

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